

Societal and personal aspects affecting the relationship between privacy awareness and the adoption of smartwatches

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ABSTRACT

Currently available research states that there are different types of influences that have an impact on the relationship between personal and societal influences for adopting Smart devices. However, currently available research does not contain information about the way in which the various personal and societal influences have an impact on this relationship. This paper examines how age, gender, education level, marketing, the influence of others and the reputation of a company influence the awareness of privacy risks and the adoption of smartwatches. The results of the study show that gender and education level have a greater effect on the awareness of privacy risks and that age, the reputation of a company, influence of others and marketing have a greater effect on the adoption of smartwatches. Finally, these correlations are substantiated by a high level of significance for the variables age, marketing, gender and the reputation of the company.

KEYWORDS

Privacy awareness, adoption, smartwatch, personal aspects, societal aspects.

INTRODUCTION

In the past decade, the amount of smart devices bought by consumers has risen significantly. According to a study by Bugeja, Jacobsson, and Davidsson (2016), the large amounts of data collected by these smart devices bring multiple privacy-related risks that can affect consumers. Think for example about Google being able to listen to recordings made by Google Assistant, which was made clear in a recent news article by Meindersma & Schellevis (2019). This means Google can listen to recordings made by millions of its customers.

The scope of this paper consists of factors influencing the relationship between the awareness of privacy risks and the adoption of smart devices. The paper first discovers a knowledge gap in the way different factors influence the relationship between the awareness of privacy risks and the adoption of smart devices. After that, the knowledge gap is further elaborated into a research question, which is then visualized into a conceptual model. Following the conceptual model, the research and data collection methods are described. Finally, the research is conducted and the results are analyzed and written up into a concise conclusion.

The results of this research can be of great value for businesses wanting to target specific audiences for selling smart devices. In addition, the results will give thoughtful insights in the proportion in which different types of factors influence the relationship between the awareness of privacy risks and the adoption of smart devices.

PROBLEM STATEMENT

First of all, when looking at currently available literature, it becomes clear that there is an evident relationship between the awareness of privacy risks and the adoption of smart devices. A study by Li, Wu, Gao, and Shi (2016) shows that the adoption of smart devices is determined by a risk-benefit analysis. In this trade-off, the benefits of adopting smart devices are weighed against the privacy-related risks of the devices. This shows an explicit relationship between the awareness of privacy risks and the adoption of smart devices. In the chapter Conceptual model & Theory, we will motivate why we chose specific societal and personal aspects among others.

Societal aspects

Furthermore, currently available literature makes it clear that there are different types of

influences that have an impact on this aforementioned relationship. A study by Jung, Kim, and Choi (2016) suggests that societal aspects, such as the brand of smartwatches, have a relatively low influence on the adoption of smartwatches. However, the research by Jung et al. (2016) focuses on the combination of brand and product quality. In this research, we focus on investigating the relationship between privacy awareness and the adoption of smart devices. Which makes the knowledge gained from the combination of brand and product quality not applicable for this research. Instead, when using societal influences, we focus more on the reputation of a company in combination with its privacy standards.

Personal aspects

Next, a study by Li et al. (2016) found that personal characteristics such as gender, education and age influence the awareness of privacy risks in general. However, there is some contradicting literature available on the effect of age on privacy awareness. Where a study by Kokolakis (2017) suggests that younger people tend to be more aware of privacy factors, a study by Li et al. (2016) states that current research on this topic contradicts each other.

Smartwatches

Looking at recent news articles, one smart device stands out. Smartwatches are one of the most discussed smart devices, especially in combination with privacy issues. An example of this is an article by Techerati (2019), which pays attention to the different types of privacy risks that smartwatches can bring to its wearers. Since a smartwatch is mostly worn for entire days, the privacy-related issues are a very interesting subject to do research on.

Knowledge gap

Concluding, the currently available research learns that there is a definite relationship between the awareness of privacy risks and the adoption of smart devices. The currently available work also states that there are different types of influences that have an impact on this relationship; personal and societal influences. However, currently available research does not contain information about the way in which the various personal and societal influences have an impact on this relationship. In addition, there is some contradicting literature regarding personal aspects.

RESEARCH QUESTION

To investigate the relations explained in the knowledge gap, the following research question has been formulated: “How do societal and personal aspects affect the relationship between awareness of privacy risks and the adoption of smartwatches?”

This main question is divided into multiple sub-questions. These are as follows:

Theoretical sub-questions

- What is the adoption of smartwatches?
- What is the awareness of privacy risks?
- What are societal aspects?
- What are personal aspects?
- How do societal aspects affect the adoption of new technologies and how societal aspects affect the awareness of privacy risks?
- How do personal aspects affect the adoption of new technologies and how do personal aspects affect the awareness of privacy risks?
- How does the awareness of privacy risks affect the adoption of new technologies?

Practical sub-questions

- To what extent do societal aspects affect the adoption of smartwatches and to what extent do societal aspects affect the awareness of privacy risks?
- To what extent do personal aspects affect the adoption of smartwatches and to what extent do personal aspects affect the awareness of privacy risks?
- To what extent does the awareness of privacy risks affect the adoption of smartwatches?

CONCEPTUAL MODEL & THEORY

To show the expected relationships between the different elements in our research question, we have designed a conceptual model (Figure 1). The conceptual model is used to visualize the concept of the research question and its variables that influences.

Figure 1: Conceptual model

H1: The effect of age on the adoption of smartwatches is stronger than the effect of age on awareness of privacy risks.

H2: The effect of gender on the awareness of privacy risks is stronger than the effect of gender on the adoption of smartwatches.

H3: The effect of education on the adoption of smartwatches is stronger than the effect of education on the awareness of privacy.

H4: There is no significant difference in the effect of the reputation of a company on the awareness of privacy risks and the effect of the reputation of a company on the adoption of smartwatches.

H5: The effect of the influence of others is stronger on the adoption of smartwatches than the effect of the influence of others on the awareness of privacy.

H6: The effect of marketing on the adoption of smartwatches is stronger than the effect of marketing on the awareness of privacy

Adoption of Smartwatches

In the research question, the adoption of smartwatches refers to the intention of consumers to buy a smartwatch and to keep using it. One of the most used models for describing technology adoption is the technology acceptance model (TAM). TAM has been applied to a wide range of technologies, including a study of smartwatch adoption (Dutot, Bhatiaisevi, Bellallahom, 2019). The model revolves around two particular elements, namely; perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use. Perceived usefulness is defined as “the degree to which a person believes that using a particular system would enhance his or her job performance” (Davis, F. (1989)). Perceived ease of use is defined as "the degree to which a person believes that using a particular system would be free of effort.” (Davis, 1989). The model implies that the behavioural intention to use is directly determined by the perceived usefulness and attitude toward usage of

products. (Davis, Fred & Bagozzi, Richard & Warshaw, 1989).

For this research on the adoption of smartwatches, it is expected that the perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness are the most important factors to take into account.

Figure 2: Technology Acceptance Model

Awareness of Privacy Risks

In this paper, the term awareness of privacy risks is used to indicate a person’s knowledge and ability to recognize potential privacy risks. The different elements that indicate a person’s awareness of privacy risks are visualized in the IPA model below.

	Type 1 Knowledge/Literacy	Type 2 Understanding	Type 3 Projection
TIPA	(Knowledge) of technical elements in information privacy	...of the technical elements in the present/current environment.	...of technologies can improve and their future implications.
RIPA	(Knowledge) of the laws that regulate the interactions.	...of how those regulations apply to the present/current environment.	...of how regulations can change its future implications.
CPIPA	(Knowledge) of the tools and practices used by organizations.	...of the common practices being used in the present/current environment.	...of how stated policy can change and its future implications.
IPA	Combination of Type 1 TIPA, RIPA and CPIPA (literacy)	Combination of Type 2 TIPA, RIPA and CPIPA	Combination of Type 3 TIPA, RIPA and CPIPA

Figure 3: A Multidimensional Model of Information Privacy Awareness (Correia and Compeau, 2017)

The elements of the IPA model are key measuring components when researching the awareness of privacy risks. The explanation of the elements is stated below:

- Technology Information Privacy Awareness (TIPA): The technical elements that are related to information privacy. In this research, the technical elements are the smartwatches and their software.
- Regulatory Information Privacy Awareness (RIPA): The regulatory elements that are related to information privacy. In this research, the laws that are applicable to smartwatches.
- Common Practices in Information Privacy Awareness (CPIPA): The common practice elements related to information privacy. In

this research, the policies and strategies that third parties use to collect, analyze, and trade private information that is generated by smartwatches.

This model divides privacy awareness into categories that can be measured in the data collection phase of this research. Measuring these components will give a comprehensive view of the participant's privacy awareness.

Societal aspects

In this paper, societal aspects are the effects at the societal level. They are measured by the reputation of the company (vendor), the influence of others, and marketing influences. We chose to use these societal aspects because these factors are commonly used in similar research, for example by Balta-Ozkan, Davidson, Bicket, and Whitmarsh (2013).

Reputation of a company

According to a study by Fuller, Serva, and Benamati (2007), competence, benevolence, and integrity are important factors for the organisations' reputation. Companies are currently facing a reputational risk by trading customer data with the possibility that the data falls into the wrong hands. As stated in the study by Balta-Ozkan et al. (2013), this risk can stop or hinder potential customers to adopt a product.

Regarding the awareness of privacy risks, there is a recent example illustrative for the impact of the reputation of a company on the awareness of privacy risks. Facebook namely contains personal information such as cell phone numbers, pictures and political preferences. According to a paper by Zunger (2018), Cambridge Analytica scraped up Facebook data from more than 50 million people and used it for political advertising purpose. Zunger (2018) describes this as the moment in which many people became aware of the privacy risks.

Influence of others

According to a paper by Kulviwat, Bruner, and Al-Shuriday (2009), societal influences have a positive effect on the adoption of innovative products. These societal influences are for example influences from people important to the potential buyer, and the expectations of others for the potential buyer to use the product.

Marketing

According to a study by Risselada, Verhoef, and Bijmolt (2014), marketers have a direct influence on consumers' behaviour. The study by

Risselada et al. (2014) states that marketing has a direct positive effect on the adoption of high-technology products.

Regarding the influence of marketing on the awareness of privacy risks, a study by Milne and Culnan (2004), states that information disclosure by marketers can improve consumer decision making and choice. According to the study by Milne and Culnan (2004), online privacy notices are intended to promote consumer choice and reduce the risks of disclosing personal information online. This shows that marketing can have a positive influence on the awareness of privacy risks.

Personal aspects

In this paper, personal aspects are the demographic characteristics that could have an effect on privacy awareness and the adoption of smartwatches. This research takes into account the following personal aspects: age, gender and education. Since these three aspects are commonly used as control variables in similar research, such as the study by Dutot et al. (2019).

Age

As mentioned in the problem statement, the effect of age on the awareness of privacy risks differs between currently available research. A study by Kokolakis (2017) suggests that younger people tend to be more aware of privacy factors, however, a study by Li et al. (2016) states that current research on this topic contradicts each other.

Regarding the adoption of new technologies, a study by Morris and Venkatesh (2000) states that younger people are generally more likely to adopt new technologies quicker than older people.

Gender

A study by Youn and Hall (2008) suggests that males tend to be more aware than females when it comes to privacy risks. In addition, a study of Li, Glass, and Records (2008) shows that men are more likely to adopt and use new technology, in comparison with women. However, the same study states that the difference in adoption between male and female is decreasing.

Education

A study by Zukowski and Brown (2007) states that people with a higher education level are often less concerned about privacy risks than people with a lower education level. In the study, privacy concerns were measured using three dimensions: control, collection, and awareness. The findings show that privacy-related concerns are shared across

all levels of education. However, people with a lower level of education generally have more concerns about the collection of personal information.

Regarding the adoption of new technology, a study of Hall and Khan (2003) shows that high levels of education are linked with high levels of technology-related skills. People with a high level of technology-related skills will generally be able to adopt new technology. In addition, a study by Chander and Thangavelu (2004) suggests that investing in a higher education level can lead to better adoption of new technologies.

Awareness of privacy risks influencing adoption

Several papers write about the influence of the awareness of privacy risks on the adoption of new technologies. A study by Xu and Gupta (2009) suggests that privacy concerns prevent consumers from using personalized location-based services. On the other hand, a study of Pentina, Zhang, Bata, and Chen (2016) suggests that privacy concerns do not prevent people to use new mobile apps that require (sensitive) personal data.

However, a study by Ernst and Ernst (2016) suggests that privacy risks have a direct negative influence on the adoption of smartwatches. The study, for example, suggests that users do not have control of their data. The users might willingly or unwillingly share their data or third parties could intercept their data. The study concludes with the statement that the extent to which a person believes that using a smartwatch could have negative consequences might be a factor to prevent people from using them in general.

METHOD & DATA COLLECTION

An online experiment was conducted to gather primary data to answer the practical research questions. Using a questionnaire enables relatively inexpensive research, and the possibility to describe the characteristics of a large population. Several questions are formulated and divided into various categories. These categories were derived from the variables used in the conceptual model. All categories except the personal aspects were measured with a 5-point Likert scale ranging from strongly disagree to strongly agree. The questionnaire contained several conditional questions to ensure questions suited the specific situation of the respondent. An overview is provided of the questions used to measure the abstract concepts. Other questions are not included in this overview, as they did not jointly measure a concept.

<p>Adoption – Ease of use</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Q1: Using a smartwatch gives me benefits over using my smartphone. • Q2: A smartwatch could help me to be more productive. • Q3: Using a smartwatch will reduce the time I spend on digital devices. • Q4: Overall, I think a smartwatch would be useful to have.
<p>Adoption – Perceived usefulness</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Q1: Learning to use my smartwatch was easy for me. • Q2: Interacting with my smartwatch is often frustrating. • Q3: I find it easy to get my smartwatch to do what I want it to do. • Q4: My smartwatch is easy to understand. • Q5: Overall, my smartwatch is easy to use.
<p>Awareness of privacy risks</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Q1 I am familiar with the presence of GPS on a smartphone. • Q2: I am aware of the data gathered by GPS of a smartphone. • Q3: I am familiar with the presence of a microphone on a smartphone. • Q4: I am aware of the data gathered by the microphone on a smartphone. • Q5: I am aware of the risks attached to authorizing/allowing companies to collect my smartphone data. • Q6: I am aware that companies distribute my smartphone data to third parties. • Q7: I am familiar with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), in dutch: Algemene Verordening Gegevensbescherming (AVG). • Q8: I am familiar with the application of the GDPR on smart devices (e.g. smartwatch, smartphone, smart home devices)

Figure 4: Overview of questions in questionnaire.

The online questionnaire was administered via Google Forms. It was available online for a period of five days, from November 6 to November 10, 2019. Before administering, the questionnaire was pre-tested and improved by three researchers to improve the validity and reliability of the research.

The survey data was analysed via a Pearson correlation test in SPSS. In this test, the correlation of the societal and personal aspects awareness and adoption was measured. The target population for the questionnaire were people living in the Netherlands who are 18 years and older. The method of convenience sampling was used as a sampling design since there was no sampling frame available. This method, as stated in the discussion section, limits the generalizability. The population was approached via social media. A consequence of this is that we do not have an equal distribution of respondents among age and education level. For a reliable result, a sample size of at least 75 and maximum 500 respondents was needed. In total, we gathered 63 responses to the questionnaire. This is less than the 75 respondents we needed, which could negatively impact the reliability of the results.

Respondents who are usually among the first adopters of new products could influence the results of the questionnaire regarding the adoption of smartwatches. To reduce this bias we included four questions which determine in which category the respondent is according to the adoption curve of Rogers (Rogers, 2003). We compared the percentage of respondents in each stage of the model with the percentage that is normal according to the adoption curve. According to the model, a normal percentage for innovators and early adopters would be 16%. Only 4.8% of the respondents answered that they would be among the first to try a new product (e.g. innovators or early adopters). In total 74.6% of the respondents say they are in the middle when it comes to trying a new technology product. We can therefore, conclude this most likely has no influence on the results of the questionnaire regarding adoption.

We also took into account that some people might not be familiar with smartwatches. In the category awareness, we used smartphones as an example. The smartphone was chosen because it has the same features as a smartwatch (e.g. GPS and microphone). Also, people might be able to relate more to a smartphone than to a smartwatch. We did not use smartphones as an example in the other categories because in these questions it was important to gather information specifically on smartwatches.

DATA ANALYSIS

The following section reviews the collected data. In addition, the survey instrument is tested for reliability and validity.

Demographic profile

Table 1 summarises the demographic profile of the respondents. The sample contained 34 male respondents (54%) and 29 female respondents (46%). The majority (84%) were between 18 and 30 years old. Most respondents (52.4%) had a degree of the University of Applied Sciences, followed by Vocational Education (17.5%).

Table 1 Demographic profile

		Count	%
Gender	Male	34	54
	Female	29	46
Age	18-30	53	84
	31-40	2	3.2
	41-50	3	4.8
	51-60	3	4.8
	> 61	2	3.2

Education	Secondary Education	12	19
	Vocational Education	11	17.5
	University of Applied Sciences	33	52.4
	University Education	7	11.1

Instrument Reliability

Reliability is the extent to which an experiment, test, or any measuring procedure yields the same results on repeated trials (Carmines and Zeller, 1979). In order to verify the reliability of the awareness of privacy risk and the adoption of smartwatches, Cronbach’s alpha was used. A Cronbach’s alpha score of 0.70 or higher is acceptable, a score of 0.80 and higher is good. The table shows that the values of all coefficients are higher than 0.70, which proves the reliability of the research.

Table 2 Reliability

	Cronbach’s Alpha
Adoption - Perceived usefulness	0.8181
Adoption - Ease of use	0.7649
Awareness of Privacy Risks	0.8961

Correlations

The table below shows an overview of all correlation coefficients. These correlations are a result of the analysis of the interview data in SPSS.

Table 3 The variables and their correlation coefficients

	Adoption of Smartwatches	Awareness of Privacy Risks
Adoption of Smartwatches	1	0.223
Awareness of Privacy Risks	0.223	1
Age	-0.357	-0.197
Gender	-0.019	-0.288
Education	0.016	0.151
Reputation of the company	0.461	0.315
Influence of others	0.510	0.164
Marketing	0.332	0.144

HYPOTHESIS AND FINDINGS

In this section, the results for the various hypotheses are given.

Hypothesis 1

H1: The effect of age on the adoption of smartwatches risks is stronger than the effect of age on awareness of privacy risks.

A Pearson correlation test was performed to identify the degree to which age influences the adoption of smartwatches and the awareness of privacy risks. A correlation coefficient of -0.357 ($p < 0.01$) demonstrated that age is negatively and significantly correlated with the adoption of smartwatches. As people get older, the extent to which they adopt smartwatches decreases. Since there is no high correlation until the correlation coefficient reaches 0.70 , this correlation can, however, be seen as a low correlation.

In this Pearson correlation test, the relationship between age and the awareness of privacy risks was also tested. A correlation coefficient of -0.197 ($p < 0.15$) displays that age is negatively and not significantly correlated with the awareness of privacy risks. As people get older, their awareness of privacy risks decreases. This correlation coefficient, however, is very low.

A comparison between the two correlation coefficients reveals that this Pearson correlation test provides evidence that supports the hypothesis. This means that the relationship between age and the adoption of smartwatches is stronger than the relationship between age and the awareness of privacy risks.

Hypothesis 2

H2: The effect of gender on the awareness of privacy risks is stronger than the effect of gender on the adoption of smartwatches.

A Pearson correlation test was performed to identify if the effect of gender on the awareness of privacy risks is stronger than the effect of gender on the adoption of smartwatches. A correlation coefficient of -0.288 ($p < 0.025$) was found, indicating that gender is negatively and significantly associated with the awareness of privacy risks. A correlation coefficient of -0.019 ($p < 0.90$) was found, indicating that gender is very low negatively correlated with the adoption of smartwatches.

These findings confirm the assertion that the effect of gender on the awareness of privacy risks is stronger than the effect of gender on the adoption of smartwatches. Hypothesis 2 is therefore supported. Furthermore, the negative correlation between

gender and the awareness of privacy risks shows that, on average, women are less aware of privacy risks than men. The results also show that the effect of being a woman has less impact on the level of adoption of smartwatches.

Hypothesis 3

H3: The effect of education on the adoption of smartwatches is stronger than the effect of education on the awareness of privacy.

A Pearson correlation test was performed to identify to what degree the education level affects the adoption of smartwatches and the awareness of privacy risks. A correlation coefficient of 0.016 ($p < 0.902$) demonstrated that education and adoption of smartwatches are not correlated and that the construct is not significant within the model. A correlation coefficient of 0.151 ($p < 0.238$) demonstrated that there is a very low positive correlation between education and the awareness of privacy risks.

A comparison between the two correlation coefficients shows that the relationship between education and awareness of privacy risks is stronger than the relation between education and adoption of smartwatches. However, both constructs are not significant within the model. The result of the correlation test is therefore inconclusive, and the hypothesis cannot be accepted.

Hypothesis 4

H4: There is no significant difference in the effect of the reputation of a company on the awareness of privacy risks and the effect of the reputation of a company on the adoption of smartwatches.

A Pearson correlation test was performed to identify to what degree the reputation of a company affects the adoption of smartwatches. A correlation coefficient of 0.461 ($p < 0.000$) demonstrates that there is a low positive correlation and that the construct is significant within the model. We can therefore conclude that there is a positive relationship between the reputation of a company and the adoption of smartwatches.

Unfortunately, due to an error in our questionnaire, we did not collect enough data to compare the effect of the reputation of a company on the awareness of privacy risks. This problem will be further elaborated in the discussion section of the paper.

Hypothesis 5

H5: The effect of the influence of others is stronger

on the adoption of smartwatches than the effect of the influence of others on the awareness of privacy.

A Pearson correlation test was performed to identify the effect of the influence of others is stronger on the adoption of smartwatches than the effect of the influence of others on the awareness of privacy. A correlation coefficient of 0.510 ($p < 0.00$) demonstrated that the influence of others has a significant moderate correlation with the adoption of smartwatches. As people have more influence of others, the extent to adopt smartwatches will increase.

A correlation coefficient of 0.164 ($p < 0.198$) demonstrated that the influence of others has a positive and not significant low correlation with the awareness of privacy.

A comparison between the two correlation coefficients reveals that this Pearson correlation test provides evidence that supports the hypothesis. This means that the relationship between the influence of others and the adoption of smartwatches is stronger than the relationship between the influence of others and the awareness of privacy risks.

Hypothesis 6

H6: The effect of marketing on the adoption of smartwatches is stronger than the effect of marketing on the awareness of privacy.

A Pearson correlation test was performed to identify the effect of marketing is stronger on the adoption of smartwatches than the effect of marketing on the awareness of privacy. A correlation coefficient of 0.332 ($p < 0.008$) demonstrated that marketing has a significant moderate correlation with the adoption of smartwatches. If people are more exposed to marketing, the extent to adopt smartwatches will increase.

A correlation coefficient of 0.144 ($p < 0.260$) demonstrated that marketing has a positive and not significant low correlation with the awareness of privacy. This means that there is a relationship between marketing and the awareness of privacy, but the influence of this relationship will most likely be low.

A comparison between the two correlation coefficients reveals that this Pearson correlation test provides evidence that supports the hypothesis. This means that the relationship between marketing and the adoption of smartwatches is stronger than the relationship between marketing and the awareness of privacy risks.

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS

The results of the hypotheses are summarized in the table below.

	Hypothesis	Results
H1	The effect of age on the adoption of smartwatches risks is stronger than the effect of age on awareness of privacy.	Age has a stronger effect on the adoption of smartwatches ($p=0.0040$) than on the awareness of privacy risks. (H1 Accepted)
H2	The effect of gender on the awareness of privacy risks is stronger than the effect of gender on the adoption of smartwatches.	Gender has a stronger effect on the awareness of privacy risks ($p=0.0219$) than on the adoption of smartwatches. (H2 Accepted)
H3	The effect of education on the adoption of smartwatches is stronger than the effect of education on the awareness of privacy.	Education has a stronger effect on the awareness of privacy risks ($p=0.238$) than on the adoption of smartwatches. (H3 Rejected)
H4	There is no significant difference in the effect of the reputation of a company on the awareness of privacy risks and the effect of the reputation of a company on the adoption of smartwatches.	Reputation of the company has a strong effect on the adoption of smartwatches ($p=0.0001$). However, there is not enough evidence to support the conjecture that there is no significant different. (H4 Rejected)
H5	The effect of the influence of others is stronger on the adoption of smartwatches than the effect of the influence of others on the awareness of privacy.	Influence of others has a stronger effect on the adoption of smartwatches ($p=0.00002$) than on the awareness of privacy risks. (H5 Accepted)
H6	The effect of marketing on the adoption of smartwatches is stronger than the effect of marketing on the awareness of privacy.	Marketing has a stronger effect on the adoption of smartwatches ($p=0.0079$) than on the awareness of privacy risks. (H6 Accepted)

Figure 5: Summary of the hypotheses results

CONCLUSION

This paper examined how age, gender, education level, marketing, the influence of others and the reputation of a company influence the awareness of privacy risks and the adoption of smartwatches. Age was found to have a significantly stronger effect on the adoption of smartwatches than on the awareness of privacy risks. In specific, the results suggest that, since the correlation coefficient is negative, older people are less likely to adopt smartwatches than younger people. This is also in line with the reviewed literature.

Furthermore, someone’s gender was found to influence their awareness of privacy risks more than the degree to which they adopt smartwatches. Generalizing, the results indicate that women on average tend to be less aware of privacy risks than men. The reputation of a company was found to have a significantly larger influence on the adoption of smartwatches than on the awareness of privacy risks. In particular, the results indicate that, as the reputation of a company improves, people will generally be more likely to adopt smartwatches.

The true effect of marketing and the influence of others on the awareness of privacy risks can not be interpreted. This is due to missing questions in the conducted survey, as stated in the limitations section. This results in an incomplete view of the effect of these two aspects. However, the results do show that the influence of others has a significant influence on the adoption of smartwatches. This suggests that the influence of others is likely to have a stronger effect on the adoption of smartwatches than on the awareness of privacy risks. In specific, the more influence of others a person will experience, the more likely that person is to adopt a

smartwatch.

In addition, the results show that marketing has a significant influence on the adoption of smartwatches. Which suggests that marketing has a higher influence on the adoption of smartwatches than on the awareness of privacy risks. This means that, as a person experiences more marketing influences, they are likelier to adopt smartwatches. In this conclusion, only significant effects were interpreted since non-significant correlation coefficients often represent less reliable results.

The figure below shows how the various personal and societal aspects influence the relationship between the awareness of privacy risks and the adoption of smartwatches:

Figure 6: Conclusion overview

DISCUSSION

Value of the conclusions

As mentioned in the introduction, the results of this research can be of value for businesses wanting to target specific audiences for selling smart devices. This research showed, for example, that the reputation of a company generally has a significant influence on the adoption. So according to this research, businesses have to take into account that their reputation has an influence on the adoption of smartwatches. Another example of a valuable conclusion is about the influence of age. The research showed that older people are less likely to adopt smartwatches than younger people. This specific information is also useful for companies when targeting specific audiences for selling smart devices.

Furthermore, the conclusions also have academic value. Current academic research learned that there is a definite relationship between the awareness of privacy risks and the adoption of smart devices. However, the available research did not contain information about the way in which the various personal and societal influences have an impact on this relationship. This study has made a valuable contribution to the knowledge base by giving new insights into how the influences impact the relationship between awareness and adoption.

Future research

The following recommendations are made for further research in this area:

Conduct additional survey research using the missing survey questions as described in the limitations. In this additional research, the sample size should be significant to gather more reliable results.

Identify additional factors that may influence the awareness of privacy risks and the adoption of smartwatches. The high significance level of some variables in this research suggests that there might be other factors that we did not take into account.

Limitations

After conducting the research we found several remarks regarding our research methods. First of all, 63 respondents filled in the questionnaire we administered. To draw reliable conclusions we should have gathered more than 75 responses. Besides, to increase the reliability of the questionnaire the research methods could be expanded by including an expert panel which reviews the questionnaire in order to get professional feedback.

We also did not add a sufficient amount of questions to the questionnaire to measure all relationships from our conceptual model. Therefore we were not able to analyze and draw conclusions for the influence of marketing and the influence of others on the awareness of privacy risks. To solve this, multiple questions should be added that measure these influences.

To test the survey, we asked a group of five respondents to fill out the questionnaire to see whether they were able to understand and answer the questions. What we did not do, however, was to analyse these responses in SPSS. By doing this, we could have made sure that all questions were stated correctly to be analysed in SPSS. If we would have done this, we could have found out we were missing two questions that were of crucial importance to measure our hypotheses.

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